

Virginity Beliefs and Gender in Malaysia: A Stigma Frame Analysis

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Abstract

Background: In various cultures, virginity is not only seen as a physiological state but an important symbol of purity as it is associated with morality, reputation within the community and family honor. The female virginity is often implicitly communicated through family and religious institutions, framing a woman's body and chastity as points of collective honor. In an era of globalization and digital connectivity, such traditional paradigms are faced with modern, interest-based beliefs that focus more in individual autonomy.

Objective: This study aims to examine the difference in virginity beliefs between women and men in Malaysia, particularly within the Stigma frame.

Methods: A cross-sectional survey was conducted among 423 Malaysian young adults aged 18-65+ years. The respondents were collected by convenience and snowball sampling techniques. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire assessing the virginity beliefs using The Virginity Beliefs Scale by Laura M. Carpenter. The scale categorizes the beliefs into Stigma, Gift and Process frames. Descriptive statistics, independent t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used to summarize the respondents characteristics. A significance level of $p=0.05$ was set.

Results: Of the 423 respondents, 52% ($n=220$) were women and 48% ($n=203$) were men and 100% of them were over the age of 18. Female respondents had significantly higher mean stigma scores ($M = 4.02$, $SD = 1.39$) compared to male respondents ($M = 3.69$, $SD = 1.31$). The difference was statistically significant ($t(421) = 6.67$, $p = 0.01$, two tailed). Consistently, a one-way ANOVA revealed a significant difference in mean stigma scores across the 2 groups ($F(1,421) = 6.67$, $p=0.01$), supporting the t-test results.

Conclusion: Female respondents have reported a higher mean stigma scores compared to male respondents. These findings highlight gender difference in beliefs within the virginity belief scale (VBS) in Malaysia.

Keywords: virginity; virginity beliefs; stigma frame; gender differences; Malaysia; adults; Virginity Beliefs Scale (VBS).

Introduction

Virginity beliefs are significant cultural and social constructs that shape one's identity, sexual conduct as well as community norms all over the world (2)(3)(4). In Malaysia, a nation known for its diversity in culture and religion, virginity is highly valued morally and socially, particularly to individuals entering adulthood (2)(3). Virginity can be generally defined as the state of never having engaged in sexual intercourse, extending beyond biology to embody the ideas of purity, familial reputation and honor especially for women (2)(4). This belief generates social expectations and pressures that contribute to stigma, internalized shame, exclusion and psychological distress (5).

Even with sexual attitudes being studied, research addressing virginity beliefs in association to stigma remains limited (2)(3). The tension between traditional values and the rising influence of globalization, liberal beliefs when it comes to sexual attitudes presents a complex environment for Malaysians to navigate (2)(4).

The conceptual framework underpinning this study is the stigma frame as explained by Carpenter where as one may feel anxious to lose their virginity, believing it to be shameful and they may feel excluded depending on their perspective with the whole matter (6).

This study aims to examine the gap in beliefs between women and men by exploring their virginity beliefs particularly in the stigma frame through a cross-sectional study and quantitative analysis. The study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the prevailing virginity beliefs among Malaysian adults?
2. How do the beliefs differ in the stigma frame between women and men?

The findings are expected to enhance understanding the difference in stigma beliefs in Malaysia between women and men as well as to inform culturally appropriate interventions aimed to reduce stigmatization.

Methods

A cross-sectional study was conducted from November 2025 to January 2026, with 423 respondents all of which were above 18 years of age and gave consent to continue with the study. The participants were selected using convenience sampling via online platforms technique and university networks. Inclusion criteria included individuals who are of Malaysian nationality, above 18 years old, are in Malaysia and consent to participate. Data was collected through a structured self-administered questionnaire comprising 3 sections: consent form, sociodemographic characteristics, and the 22 virginity beliefs scale questions. The 22 questions were assessed with a Likert-scale (7) which has been validated with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.89, measuring all 3 frames in the VBS which are; Stigma, Gift and Process. Within the scale, questions 1,6,8,11,15,17,19 and 21 fall under the stigma frame. The results from the Likert-scale were summed and divided by 8 (the number of questions) to get the mean.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS and JASP. Descriptive statistics (means, standard deviations, frequencies, and percentages) summarized the respondents' demographics and variable distribution. Differences in stigma scores across the 2 groups, women and men were assessed via Independent *t*-tests and one-way ANOVA. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from SEGi University. Participants provided consent, and confidentiality was maintained throughout the study. Names, phone numbers and emails were not collected to maintain anonymity.

Results

Of the 423 respondents, 52% (n=220) were women and 48% (n=203) were men and 100% of them were over the age of 18. Within the scale, questions 1,6,8,11,15,17,19 and 8 fall under the stigma frame. The results from the Likert-scale were summed and divided by 8 to get the mean. Female respondents had significantly higher mean stigma scores ($M = 4.02$, $SD = 1.39$) compared to male respondents ($M = 3.69$, $SD = 1.31$). The difference was statistically significant ($t(421) = 6.67$, $p = 0.01$, two tailed). Consistently, a one-way ANOVA revealed a significant difference in mean stigma scores across the 2 groups ($F(1,421) = 6.67$, $p = 0.01$), supporting the t-test results. In conclusion, women reported significantly higher stigma scores compared to men.

Figure 1: Pie chart showing the gender distribution of the 423 respondents

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of Stigma mean scores with gender

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Female	220	4.0295	1.39070	.09376	3.8448	4.2143	1.63	7.00
Male	203	3.6890	1.31463	.09227	3.5071	3.8710	1.63	6.63
Total	423	3.8661	1.36380	.06631	3.7358	3.9965	1.63	7.00

Table 2: Independent Samples Test for Stigma mean and Gender

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Stigma Mean	Equal variances assumed	.209	.648	2.583	421	.010	.34051	.13185	.08135	.59966
	Equal variances not assumed			2.588	420.750	.010	.34051	.13155	.08193	.59908

Table 3: ANOVA (Stigma) mean for gender between and within groups

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	12.241	1	12.241	6.670	.010
Within Groups	772.663	421	1.835		
Total	784.904	422			

Discussion

The stigma frame showed noticeable difference between female respondents and male respondents. Male respondents scored ($M = 3.69$, $SD = 1.31$) $p = 0.01$ whereas female respondents scored ($M = 4.02$, $SD = 1.39$) $p = 0.01$ suggesting that female respondents feel more stigmatized when it comes to the concept of virginity. Multiple studies have reported that male adolescents are significantly more likely to report having had premarital sex compared to female adolescents, suggesting that gendered differences in behavior reflect underlying trauma (7). In a large school survey, 8.3% of male adolescents reported ever having had sexual intercourse compared to only 2.9% of females, indicating lower female participation or lower reporting among females, likely due to stigma and societal norms against females engaging in premarital sex (7). These gender differences are observed with a broader pattern in Malaysian sexual behavior research, where under-reporting by girls is widely attributed to moral stigma, fear of judgement, and gendered expectations around chastity (7)(8). While many Malaysian studies focus on predictors rather than stigma per se, the consistent finding of higher male prevalence and lower female reporting is widely translated in the public health literature as driven by differential gender stigma and normative expectations (9). One of the significant questions on attitudes to virginity for women is “Are they maintaining their virginity, based on their individual attitudes and decisions or for maintaining socio-cultural structures or moral obligations?”(10). Undeniably, violence against women due to being not virgin is still happening around the world, some are coming through the limelight while some are happening in silence in fear of stigmatization (11). Gender-sensitive interventions are necessary as gender norms not only shape differential experiences of stigma but influence access and utilization of sexual and reproductive health services as systematic reviews demonstrate that deeply entrenched gender roles negatively affect women’s ability to make informed health decisions (12).

While this study contributes valuable insights, limitations must be acknowledged. The cross-sectional design precludes casual inference and the use of online platforms may limit full results due to factors such as boredom and inadequacy in understanding. Finally, the reliance on the VBS, although psychometrically validated, it may not capture the full complexity or nuance of virginity beliefs across diverse cultural contexts, limiting generalizability of the results.

Conclusion

The study demonstrates that virginity beliefs within the sample remain predominantly around gender-laden and moralized frameworks, with the Stigma frame scores presenting a significant difference between women and men. Understanding this nuanced belief pattern is essential for developing culturally sensitive sexual health interventions and educational programs.

Longitudinal studies could provide an insight into how these beliefs evolve over time and across different social contexts.

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